
Synthesis, characterization, antibacterial and antifungal activities of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Schiff base complexes derived from methionine and salicylaldehyde

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Abstract The ligand, methioninesalicylidene (MTS) was synthesized at room temperature by the condensation reaction of methionine and salicylaldehyde. The synthesized ligand was used to prepare the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes. The ligand and its complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductivity, magnetic susceptibility, infrared spectra and UV-Vis spectra data. The melting points of the ligand and the complexes were high (300-342°C) while the molar conductivity values were low. The infrared spectra data described that the ligand as tridentate molecule coordinating to the metal ions through its azomethine nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen atoms of the ligand moiety. The UV spectra data obtained suggest octahedral geometry for the complexes. The results from the antibacterial and antifungal studies showed that the metal complexes have higher antibacterial activities than antifungal activities. In all cases, metal complexes proved to be better antimicrobial agents when compared to the free ligand.

Keywords Synthesis, Characterization, Schiff base, Complex, antibacterial, antifungal

Introduction

Schiff bases also called imines are compounds characterized by the presence of the azomethine group (C=N). They are formed when an aldehyde or a ketone react with an amine [1]. This reaction is known to proceed best at a pH of 4 or 5 as below and above these pH values the reaction may be slow or may not occur [1-3]. Although recent studies have shown that Schiff bases can also be synthesized under solvent free conditions using catalysts [4,5]. Schiff bases are known to form very stable complexes with the transition metals [6]. These transition metals are able to form complexes with Schiff bases because they have vacant d orbitals which are ready to accept the electrons donated by the Schiff base ligands [7]. In recent times, studies on Schiff bases and their metal complexes have attracted a lot of attention due to their biological, pharmacological, industrial, material science and catalytic applications [8]. Studies have shown that Schiff bases and their complexes are potential antimicrobial, antitumor, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, analgesics, and cytotoxicity agents [9].

This research work focuses on the synthesis, characterization, antibacterial and antifungal activities of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Schiff base complexes derived from methionine and salicylaldehyde.

Experimental Work

Materials

All chemicals used for this research were of analytical grade purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used without

further purification. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were obtained using Perkin Elmer PE240 automatic elemental analyzer, Shimadzu Perkin Elmer Infrared BX Spectrophotometer, Perkin Elmer Lambda 25 UV-visible spectrophotometer, Pico Lab India conductivity meter, Gouy balance using copper sulphate as standard material for measurement of magnetic susceptibility, Gallenkamp melting point apparatus, UNISCOPE SM 9053 Laboratory oven, nutrient agar, potato dextrose agar, autoclave,

Synthesis of the Schiff base ligand- methioninesalicylidene (MTS)

Ethanol solution (30ml) of salicylaldehyde (10mmol, 0.121g) was added to 30ml ethanolic solution of methionine (10mmol, 0.149g). Three drops of glacial acetic acid were added. The resulting mixture was stirred magnetically for 2 hours and the solution was left to stand overnight [2]. The white precipitate formed was filtered, washed with methanol and dried over anhydrous fused calcium chloride in a desiccators. Percentage yield (63%).

Equation for the reaction:

Synthesis of the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes

The complexes were synthesized by mixing equimolar solutions of the Schiff base ligand and the metal (II) chlorides in 30ml ethanol. The mixture was stirred magnetically for 2 hours after which it was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride in a desiccator [2,3].

Results

Table 1: Physical Properties of MTS and its complexes

complex/ ligand	Colour	% yield	Melting point (°C)	Conductivity ($\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$)	Found(Cald)%			
					C	H	N	S
MTS	White	63	250	1.01	56.92	5.93	5.53	12.65
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{NSO}_3$					(57.02)	(5.93)	(5.48)	(12.08)
$\text{Co}(\text{MTS})_2$	Brown	55	300	1.06	51.16	4.97	4.97	11.37
$\text{CoC}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$					(50.98)	(4.84)	(4.79)	(12.05)
$\text{Cu}(\text{MTS})_2$	Pale	81	320	2.03	50.74	4.93	4.93	11.28
$\text{CuC}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$	green				(50.64)	(4.89)	(4.10)	(12.00)
$\text{Ni}(\text{MTS})_2$	Blue	48	342	1.07	51.16	4.97	4.97	11.37
$\text{NiC}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$					(51.20)	(5.00)	(4.68)	(11.35)

Table 2: Infrared spectra of MTS and its complexes (cm^{-1})

Ligand/ complexes	$\nu(\text{phenolic OH})$	$\nu(\text{C=N})$	$\nu(\text{C-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-S})$
MTS	3432	1591	1083	-	-	
$\text{Co}(\text{MTS})_2$	3275	1580	1059	574	469	389
$\text{Ni}(\text{MTS})_2$	3288	1614	1073	582	393	394
$\text{Cu}(\text{MTS})_2$	3275	1575	1074	592	459	393

Table 3: Electronics Spectra and Assignments

Compound	χ_m (μ_s)	$\sqrt{cm^{-1}}$	Assignment	Geometry
MTS		47619	$n \rightarrow \sigma^*$	
		33670	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
		29498	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	
Co(MTS) ₂	6.280x10 ⁻⁶ (3.82)	15746	$^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}$	Octahedral
		21276	$^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}$	
		23640	$^4T_{1g} \rightarrow T_{1g}$	
Ni(MTS) ₂	3.340x10 ⁻⁶ (2.68)	18518	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$	Octahedral
		23809	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$	
Cu(MTS) ₂	1.260x10 ⁻⁶ (1.63)	31000	$^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$	Octahedral
		16949	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$	

Table 4: Antimicrobial properties of the MTS and its metal complexes

	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. digitatum</i>
MTS	10	9	7	9	8	7	7
Co(MTS) ₂	10	8	9	11	11	8	9
Ni(MTS) ₂	11	11	9	12	9	9	7
Cu(MTS) ₂	14	11	12	12	10	9	8
Ampiclox/ Fluconazole	25	22	21	22	22	23	22

Figure 1: Antimicrobial properties of the MTS and its metal complexes

Figure 2: Line plot for antimicrobial properties of the MTS and its metal complexes

Discussion

Physical Properties

The synthesized compounds are differently coloured ranging from brown, green to blue depending on their wavelengths of maximum absorption. The molar conductivities of the ligand and the complexes were low revealing their non-electrolytic nature [10]. The complexes also displayed high melting points ranging from 250 to 340°C due to the strong bonding network formed between the ligand and the metal ions [11].

Infrared Spectra

The infrared spectral data of the ligand and its complexes is presented on Table 2. From the IR spectra of the ligand, the vibrational frequencies at 1591 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching. This band exhibited a systematic shift to higher frequencies of 1610 cm⁻¹, 1605 and 1614 cm⁻¹ in the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) spectra respectively suggesting coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal ions. The broad band at 3432 cm⁻¹ for phenolic OH on the spectrum of the ligand disappeared for a weak node at lower frequencies at 3275 cm⁻¹, 3275 cm⁻¹ and 3288 cm⁻¹ in the complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) respectively. This also suggests the deprotonation and subsequent coordination of the oxygen atom of the phenolic group to the metal ions. The bands between 574- 592 cm⁻¹ assigned to the M-N and 393-469cm⁻¹ for M-O stretching vibrations affirm these coordination. The tridentate coordination is supported by the band at 810cm⁻¹ which is assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ in the free ligand, is shifted to lower wave numbers in the complexes suggesting the change of bond order and strong electron delocalization upon complexation[15].

Electronic Spectra

The UV-visible spectra of the synthesized compounds are shown in Table 3. The uv spectrum of the ligand gave bands at 47,619 cm⁻¹, 33,670 cm⁻¹ and 29,498 cm⁻¹ due to $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ intra-ligand transitions. The electronic spectrum of [Cu(MTS)₂] consists of two bands 31,000cm⁻¹ and 16949cm⁻¹. These correspond to ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ transitions respectively. These spectral pattern in combination with magnetic susceptibility value (χ_m) of 1.260×10^{-6} indicating the present of an unpaired electron show a distorted octahedral geometrical configuration around the copper(II) complex [12]. The spectrum of the [Co(MTS)₂] consists of three bands at 15748 cm⁻¹, 21276 cm⁻¹ and 23640 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow \text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions respectively. The transitions and the magnetic susceptibility value (χ_m) of 6.280×10^{-6} indicate the present of three unpaired electrons and therefore conform to an outer sphere octahedral complex. The spectrum of Ni(MTS)₂ has two bands at 18518cm⁻¹ and 23809cm⁻¹. These correspond to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions. The magnetic susceptibility reflecting the present of two unpaired electrons affirm the octahedral configuration of this complex [13,14].

Antimicrobial Analysis

The antimicrobial studies were carried out by the disc diffusion method and the results compared to that of ampiclox and fluconazole. The results showed that the complexes have better antimicrobial properties than the free ligand. The bacteria used for the studies were: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Eschereshia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Proteus mirabilis* while the fungi were: *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Penicillum digitatum*. The complexes were seen to have higher antibacterial activities but less effective on the fungi strains studied. The [Cu(MTS)₂] had highest antibacterial effect.

Conclusion

The synthesized ligand exhibits tridentate nature, coordinating to the metals through the azomethine nitrogen, sulphur atom and the phenolic oxygen. The complexes were formed from a 2:1 ligand to metal molar ratio with distorted and normal octahedral geometrical configuration affirmed by the spectral data for Cu(II) Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes respectively. The antimicrobial studies revealed that the complexes show higher inhibitory activities than the free ligand.

Where M= Co(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II)

Figure 2: The metal (II) complexes

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